

16 Śiva Temples at Barukheda

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The village Barukheda is located in Neemuch Tehsil of Mandsaur district in Madhya Pradesh. It is situated 4 kms. north of Neemuch city and is approached by Jeep. There is a *kachcha* road from Neemuch to Barukheda. There are four temples at Barukheda which belong to *circa* 12th century A.D. All of these were built during the reign of Paramaras of Malwa. These temples have been referred to in the Administration report, Gwalior Archaeological Department, 1914-22. Three of them are dedicated to Śiva. However, the fourth one which is located inside the village, was also originally dedicated to Śiva but has been converted into a Viṣṇu temple and an image of Chārabhujāji has been installed in it. These temples are at present neither under the protection of the State nor the Central Government.

ŚIVA TEMPLE NO. 1

This temple is located on the southern outskirts of the village inside the field of Shri Bherulal Meghwar on a platform measuring 48 cms. high and faces west. It consists on plan of a *pañcharatha* sanctum, an *antarāla*, a *mahāmaṇḍapa* with lateral transepts and an *ardhamaṇḍapa* (pl. 14). The sanctum measures 2.19 mt. square. The walls of the sanctum are plain except for a niche in the northern, eastern and southern walls. There is a plain pilaster at each of the four corners of the sanctum which supports plain brackets. The ceiling of the sanctum is supported by four pilasters and eight brackets. The architrave of the ceiling is plain and supports two squares, one inside the other. The top of the ceiling is decorated with a full-blown lotus. The niche in the eastern wall of the sanctum is composed of two

rectangular pilasters which support a *chhādya* and a pediment of *chaitya*-arches decorated in the centre with a full-blown lotus.

Sanctum-Doorway

The sanctum-doorway consists of three *sākhās*. The first *sākhā* is decorated with lotus-creeper. The second is carved with three panels each containing *mithunas* in erotic posture and the third is carved with lotus-petals. The lintel of the sanctum-doorway shows four-armed Śiva standing in *samapāda* inside a niche. He carries *varada*, mutilated *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. His head and his upper right hand have been chopped off. On the right end of the lintel is carved four-armed and three-headed bearded Brahmā standing in *samapāda* and carrying *sruk* and *pustaka* by his only surviving upper right and upper left hands. His lower right hand is in *varada* while his lower left hand has been chopped off. Both the pilasters of the niche have been chopped off. The left end of the lintel shows four-armed Viṣṇu standing in *samapāda* and carrying chopped off, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha*. The interspaces between the *lalāṭabimbā* and the sculptures of Brahmā and Viṣṇu is filled

pl. 14 Śiva temple No. 1, general view
from west, Barukheda (Mandsaur).

up with standing *navagrahas*. While Sūrya is standing in *samapāda* and holds lotuses by both of his hands, the next six *grahas* are seen standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *abhaya* and *kamaṇḍalu*. Only the head of Rāhu has been shown while Ketu is depicted in the form of serpent. All the three *sākhās* of the doorway have been carried over on the lintel. Above the sanctum-doorway are seen three niche-shrines, two of which contain each a diamond design while the third or the central one contains an image of a four-armed devī seated in *lalitāsana* on a corpse and carrying *pāśa* and *aṅkuśa* by her upper right and left hands. Her lower right hand has been chopped off while her lower left hand carries an indistinct object. The interspace between the niches and the walls of the *antarāla* is filled up with ten panels each containing a diamond. The lower portion of the sanctum-doorway is carved with figure sculptures. The right flank of the sanctum-doorway shows (1) two-armed Gaṅgā standing in *tribhaṅga*. Her breasts and left hand carrying a *kalaśa* have been chopped off. (2) A niche containing an image of four-armed Śaiva *dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying chopped off, *triśūla*, *khaṭvāṅga* and *kalaśa*. He wears *jaṭāmukuta*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *yajñōpavīta*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpuras*, a long *mālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. His head and lower right hand have been chopped off. (3) A *māle* attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* in *aṅjalimudrā*.

The left flank of the sanctum doorway shows (1) two-armed Yamunā standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *kalaśa* by her upraised left hand. The mount tortoise is carved below her. (2) A niche containing an image of four-armed Śaiva-*dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. He wears dress and ornaments similar to the dress and ornaments of Śaiva *dvarapāla* on the right flank. (3) A male attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* in *aṅjalimudrā*.

The door-sill is carved in the centre with a *mandāraka* showing spiral-lotus-stalk flanked on either side by four panels, three of which contain half-diamond design while the fourth contains a full diamond design. The doorsill is carved on the right end with a panel containing a diamond design and a niche containing an image of four-armed Kubera seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada*, *nakulaka*, *nakulaka* and *bījapūraka*. The niche is flanked on the left by a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga*. The left end of the doorsill shows a niche containing an image of four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *paraśu*, lotus-stalk, lotus-stalk and *modakapātra*. The niche is flanked on the right by a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga*. On the left of the niche is a panel containing a diamond design. In front of the doorway is a *chandraśilā* carved with lotus-petals and a band of diamonds on the border. It is flanked on either side by *śaikhā* and *padma*.

Antarāla

The walls of the *antarāla* are plain except for a niche in the southern and northern walls. Each niche is composed of two rectangular pilasters and is surmounted by a *Kūtachhādyā* decorated with rafter motif. Both of these niches are lying vacant at present. The left pilaster of the niche on the southern wall is missing. On the southern wall is carved a mason mark *sūtradhāra dhala*. On the northern wall is carved a mason mark reading *sūtradhāra Moṭā*. The

pl. 15 Śiva temple No. 1, Dancing
Chāmuṇḍā on the northern bhadra,
Barukheda.

ceiling of the *antarāla* rests on two pilasters each of which consist of a base, a shaft and a capital. The base of the pilaster consists of plain *bhitta*, *khura* and *kumbha* decorated with a half-diamond design. The shaft is octagonal in the lower portion, sixteen sided in the middle portion and circular at the top where it is decorated with an octagonal band. Above the shaft rests the capital which consists of a *padma*. Above the capital rests the plain bracket which supports plain architrave of the ceiling of the *antarāla*. The *antarāla* measures 94 cms. long 2.33 cms. broad.

Mahāmaṇḍapa

The ceiling of *mahāmaṇḍapa* rests on two pilasters of *antarāla* and eight pillars which are located over a 1.03 mt. high parapet wall. Each of the pillars measures 1.97 mt. high including brackets. Above the brackets rests the plain architrave of the ceiling. Above the architrave rests the ceiling which consists of ten bands of concentric, overlapping circles. The top of the ceiling is decorated with a full-blown lotus. At the base of the ceiling are fixed twelve plain brackets which supported figures of 12 standing *surasundarīs* which are now missing. Only the feet of two *surasundarīs* are seen on two brackets. Above each bracket is a socket which held the *surasundarī* in her position. This is a beautiful ceiling of *nābhichhanda variety*.

Transepts of the mahāmaṇḍapa

Each of the transepts of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* measures 75 cms. long and 2.06 mt. broad. The inter-space between the outer pillars of the lateral transepts has been filled up by construction of a wall having a *mihrab* during the Islamic rule in circa 15th century A.D. This is a later addition to the temple and must be removed in order to expose the original

temple. The ceiling of the transept rests on four pillars of which two are in common with the *mahāmaṇḍapa*. Each of the two outer pillars of the transepts consists of a square shaft which becomes octagonal in the middle and circular at the top and supports the capital which consists of a *padma*. Each of the transepts has a cell in the lower portion corresponding with the parapet wall in the *mahāmaṇḍapa*. The *mahāmaṇḍapa* measures 4.42 mt. square.

Ardhamanḍapa

The ceiling of the *ardhamanḍapa* rests on four pillars of which two are in common with *mahāmaṇḍapa*. The two outer pillars of *ardhamanḍapa* stand over the *kakshāsana* and consist of a shaft which is square in the lower portion, octagonal in the middle portion and circular at the top where it is decorated with plain octagonal band. Above the shaft rests the capital which consists of a *padma* and supports plain brackets having a single volute. The brackets support the plain architrave of the ceiling which is surmounted by a *kūtachhādyā* on the exterior side. The ceiling of the *ardhamanḍapa* consists of an octagon supporting a square and a parallelogram which contains a full-blown lotus. The pillars of the *ardhamanḍapa* rest on the parapet wall which measures 1.06 mt. high. The *ardhamanḍapa* measures 2.19 mt. long and 2.39 mt. broad. Inside the *manḍapa* are lying two fragments of the original *yōnipatta*, which was installed inside the sanctum. Each of the fragments measures 35 cms. high. The *ardhamanḍapa* is approached by a flight of four steps on the western side.

pl. 19 Śiva temple No. 4, general view
from south-west, Barukheda.

Elevation

In elevation, the temple shows from bottom upwards *pīṭha* mouldings consisting of a *kharasīlā*, *bhīṭṭa*, *jādyakumbha*, *kārnikā*, and a *kapota*. Above this rest the *adhiṣṭhāna* mouldings which consist of a *ratna-khura*, *ratna-kumbha* decorated with half-diamond design and a plain median band, plain *kalāśa*, plain *antarpatra* and double *kapota* decorated with *kuḍūs*. Above the *adhiṣṭhāna* mouldings rests the *jañghā* which is decorated on each of the three *bhādras* with a niche containing an image of *parivāradēvata* and a median band carved with *kīrttimukhas*.

The sculptures on the jañghā

A niche on the northern *bhadra* contains an image of sixteen-armed dancing Chāmuṇḍā on a corpse (pl. 15). She carries *kapāla*, *ghanṭā trisūla*, *vajra*, *aṅkuśa patākā hasta*, *sarpa*, string of a bow, *sarpa*, *damaru*, chopped off, *pāśa*, *muṇḍa*, *kapāla* and arrow. She wears *jaṭāmukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *sarpa-hāra*, *sarpa-keyūras*, *sarpa-valayas*, *sarpa nūpurās*, *muṇḍa-mālā* and a scarf fastened by a *sarpa mekhala*. She is flanked on the right by a goblin standing in *tribhāṅga* and carrying dagger and *kapāla*. Behind her is shown a standing buffalo with its upraised head sucking the blood from the *muṇḍa* held by Chāmuṇḍā who is represented with emaiated body and a scorpion is seen on her belly. She has ferocious look with bulging eyes and protruding teeth. She has drooping breasts. The peculiarity of this sculpture is that here besides the scorpion is also shown a buffalo mount.

pl. 16 Śiva temple No. 1, Natarāja on the southern bhādra, Barukheda.

The niche on the eastern bhādra contains an image of four-armed Viṣṇu standing *samapāda* and carrying *gadā* and *chakra* in his only surviving upper right and left hands. Both of his lower hands and all the attributes held by him have been chopped off. He wears a *kīrītamukuta* and is flanked on either side by an attendant standing in *tribhāṅga*. The sculpture is painted with modern red paint.

The niche on the southern bhādra contains an image of fourteen-armed Natarāja carrying *varadhāksha*, *khatvāṅga*, *triśūla*, *nrityamudrā*, *śrīṅga*, *damaru*, *sarpa*, *sarpa*, *kapāla*, *khatvāṅga*, *viṅā*, *pāsa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. He wears *jatā-mukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *yajñōpavīta*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels (pl. 16). On his right is carved a male drummer in front of whom are placed two drums. On his left is carved a flying human figure. This is a very good sculpture of Natarāja.

Śikhara

Above the *jaṅghā* rest the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings which consist of double *padma* and *kapota*. Above the *kapota* are plain brackets which support the *kūṭachhādyā*. Above the *kūṭachhādyā* rests the *śikhara* which is decorated with one row of *urahśrīṅgas* and two rows of *karnaśrīṅgas*. The portion of the *śikhara* above the *grīvā* is missing. The *śikhara* of the sanctum is over-grown with vegetation. The roof of the *mahāmandapa* is domical and is in a dilapidated condition. The roof of the *mandapa* is flat and is decorated on the border with merlons.

The mouldings of the *mahāmandapa* and *ardhamandapa* are common with the sanctum upto the level

of *kumbha*. In case of *mahāmandapa* and *ardhamandapa*, the *kumbha* is surmounted by plain *vedikā* mouldings which support the *āsanapaṭṭa* and *kakshāsana* decorated with various floral, geometrical, animal, human and divine motifs such as rosettes, *kīrttimukhas*, *haṁsas*, Gaṇeśa and vase-and-foliage.

The wall constructed in between the pillars of lateral transept of *mahāmandapa* during the Muslim rule looks ugly and is an eye-sore which should be removed in order to expose the originality of the temple. The temple is over-grown with vegetation. The pavement, platform and steps are in a very bad shape and require attention for repairs. If urgent steps are not taken to carry out the repairs, there is every possibility of further deterioration of the temple. The temple is in a neglected state and deserves to be protected.

ŚIVA TEMPLE NO. 2

This temple is located on the south of the village at a distance of about 150 mt. on the north of Śiva temple No. 1 in the field of Shri Shankar Lal. The temple consists on plan of a *pañcharatha* sanctum, an *antarāla* and a *mahāmandapa* (pl. 17)

Sanctum

The sanctum measures 2.60 mt. square. The walls of the sanctum are plain except for a niche in the northern, southern and eastern walls. The niche in the eastern wall is composed of two rectangular pilasters and is surmounted by a *chhādyā* which supports a small pediment carved with a diamond design. While the niche on the eastern wall measures 1.21 mt. high, 73 cms. broad and 33 cms. deep, the niches in the northern and southern walls measure each 61 cms. high, 46 cms. broad and 39 cms. deep. The ceiling of the sanctum is supported by eight plain pilasters, two at each of the four corners which support the brackets. These pilasters and additional four brackets support the plain architrave of the ceiling. The ceiling consists of two octagons and two squares, one above the other. The ceiling is carved with a full-blown lotus. At present there is no image inside the sanctum. All the niches are also lying vacant. There is a crack in the northern wall and the pavement of the floor of the sanctum is in a very bad shape and disturbed condition.

The sanctum-doorway measures 1.81 mt. high, 88 cms. wide and 61 cms. deep. It consists of three plain *sākhas*. The second *sākhā* being *rūpastambha* is decorated with vase and foliage motif at the top. On the left flank of the sanctum-doorway on the second *sākhā* are carved the names of two masons Sūtradhara *sākhā* and Sūtradhar *Nāthu*. The names of other masons Monga and Sagar are carved on the lintel of the sanctum-doorway. The *lalāṭabimba* shows four-armed seated Gaṇeśa. On either end of the lintel is carved a panel containing a diamond design. There is a wide crack in the lintel of the sanctum-doorway. Above the lintel are carved thirteen panels each containing a diamond. The door-sill shows a chopped *maṇḍāraka* in the centre which was flanked on either side by *kīrttimukha* and a panel containing a diamond design. The *kīrttimukha* on the left has been chopped off.

Antarāla

The walls of the *antarāla* are plain except for a niche in the northern and southern walls. Each niche measures 67 cms. high, 40 cms. wide and 27 cms., deep. These niches are

composed of two rectangular pilasters and are surmounted by a plain pediment. They are lying vacant at present. The *antarāla* measures 1.46 m. long and 2.37 cms. broad. The ceiling of the *antarāla* rests on two pilasters each of which has a square base decorated with half-diamond design, a shaft which is square in the lower portion, octagonal and sixteen-sided in the middle portion and circular at the top where it is carved with four *kīrttimukhas* from which hang a chain-and-bell. The shaft supports the capital which consists of a plain *padma* surmounted by a plain bracket with a single volute. Above the bracket rests the plain architrave which is carved on the side of *mahāmaṇḍapa* and *garbhagrīha* with a *kīrttimukha*. The lower portion of the architrave is carved with a louts. The ceiling of the *antarāla* is decorated with four full-blown lotuses.

Mahāmaṇḍapa

Mahāmaṇḍapa measures 4.82 mt. square. The ceiling of *mahāmaṇḍapa* rests on twelve pilasters of which two are in common with the pilasters of *antarāla*. The pilasters of *mahāmaṇḍapa* have the same ornamentation and design except the four pilasters at the corners. They are similar to the pilasters of *antarāla* described earlier. There are two niches in the eastern wall of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* of which the one in the northeast corner is in dilapidated condition. Each of the niches measures 1.06 mt. high and 62 cms. wide. Each of them is 29 cms. deep. There are two mihrabs which have been carved on two walls in between the pilasters of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* on the western side. It shows that the Mohammadans have constructed the mihrab, for offering prayer inside the temple. The ceiling of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* on the southwestern corner has collapsed and the ruins are lying inside the *mahāmaṇḍapa*. The ceiling has an architrave carved with three friezes, the lowest carved with lotus-foilage issuing out of a *kīrttimukha*, the middle one decorated with diamonds in panels while the upper one engraved with rosettes in panels. Above the architrave rests the ceiling which consists of over-lapping concentric circles. On the second circle from the bottom are carved 12 *bhūta*-brackets each showing a flying *gaṇa*. The *gaṇas* are as follows:

1. A *gaṇa* holding a *kapāla* by his right hand.
2. A *gaṇa* in *añjalimudrā*.
3. A *gaṇa* carrying a garland.
4. A *gaṇa* whose hands have been chopped off.

5. A *gaṇa* with his right hand upraised and left hand kept on the belly.
6. A *gaṇa* who has his right upraised hand kept on his head and left hand kept on the chest.
7. A *gaṇa* holding a sword by his right hand. His left hand is kept on his belly.
8. A *gaṇa* playing on a flute.
9. A *gaṇa* playing on a drum.
10. A *gaṇa* playing on a drum.
11. A *gaṇa* in *tarjanī-mudrā* with the *tarjanī* of his right hand placed on his lip.
12. A collapsed *gaṇa* playing on *Vīṇā*.

Above these *gaṇas* were twelve figures of *surasundarīs* which are now missing. There is a socket on the six circles which held *surasundarīs* in position. It is interesting to note that in the third circle from the top is carved an inscription of four lines which is dt. VS 1624 (A.D. 1567). This inscription requires to be studied thoroughly. The top of the ceiling is carved with a full-blown lotus. The *mahāmaṇḍapa* has three doorways, one on the western side or the front side and one each on the northern and southern sides. Each of these doorways measures 1.81 mt. high, 90 cms. wide and 64 cms. deep. Each doorway is carved with three *sākhas*, all of which are plain. The second *sākha* is a *rūpastambha* which is engraved with foliage at the top. The lower portion of the *sākha* is carved with a panel containing a diamond design. On the door-lintel is carved an image of Gaṇeśa. The images of Gaṇeśa are seen seated on the

pl. 17 Śiva temple No. 2, general view from south, Barukheda.

northern and western doorway, while the image of Gaṇeśa on the southern doorway is seen standing. At either end of the doorway-lintel is carved a panel containing a diamond design. The doorsill of each of the doorways shows a *mandāraka* in the centre flanked on either side by a *kīrtimukha*. The name of the architect Muñja is also carved on the circle from the top of the ceiling of the *mahāmaṇḍapa*. The doorways on the northern and southern sides are in dilapidated condition. In front of each of the doorways is a *chandraśilā*. Each of the doorways is approached by a flight of four steps. The steps of the doorways on the western and southern sides have collapsed and are missing. Near the doorways are growing a number of thorny bushes. Inside the *mahāmaṇḍapa* is kept a mutilated *yōnipaṭṭa* which was original. It is circular and measures 34 cms. high. It is broken into two pieces. From this *yōnipaṭṭa* it is clear that this temple belongs to Śiva.

Elevation

The temple stands on a platform or *jagatī* measuring 1.30 mt. high. The *pīṭha* mouldings consist of two plain *bhūttas*, *jādyakumbha*, *karnikā*, *kapota* and a number of *paṭṭikās*. Above this start the *adhishṭhāna* mouldings which show *khura* carved with diamonds, *kumbha* decorated with a median band of diamonds and rosettes, plain *kalaśa*, plain *antarpatra* and double *kapota* decorated with *kuḍūs*. Above this rests the plain *jañghā* carved with two plain bands, one in the middle and the other on the top. On the *bhadras* of the *jañghā* on the northern, eastern and southern sides is a niche composed of rectangular pilasters and surmounted by a *chhādyā* and a small pediment of *chaitya*-arches. Each of the three *bhadra*-niches is lying vacant at present. The *jañghā* is surmounted by *varaṇḍikā* mouldings which consist of four plain mouldings one of which is carved with foliage and the other with lotus-petals. Above the *varaṇḍikā* rests *kūṭachhādyā* supported by plain brackets. Above this *kūṭachhādyā* is the *śikhara* which is also *pañcharatha* and is decorated with a cluster of *urahśringas* and *karna śriṅgas*. Each side of the *śikhara* shows three *urahśriṅgas* and two rows, each consisting of two miniature *śikharas*, on the *karnaśriṅgas*. The *śikhara* is surmounted by three *āmalakas*. The *chandrikā*, *kalaśa* and *bijapūraka* above the *śikhara* have collapsed and are missing.

The roof of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* is domical but the dome is exposed to the weather. Its core can be seen as its plaster has deteriorated and is missing. The temple is surmounted by thorny bushes. The vegetation is growing above the temple also. Its platform is in a ruined condition.

ŚIVA TEMPLE NO. 3

This temple is located on the northwestern corner of the village Barukheda. The temple is located near the field of Gautam Mali. It consists on plan of a sanctum, an *antarāla* and an *ardhamandapa* (pl. 18).

Sanctum

The sanctum is *pañcharatha* on plan and is surmounted by a *pañcharatha śikhara*. It measures 1.88 mt. square. It has plain walls. The temple faces east unlike the temple Nos. 1, 2 & 4 which face west. The southern, northern and western walls have each a niche which is lying vacant at present. The niche in the western wall is larger than the niches on the southern and northern walls. It measures 80

cms. high, 52 cms. wide and 21 cms. deep. The niches in the northern and southern walls are of equal size, and each of them measures 55 cms. high, 42 cms. wide and 22 cms. deep. The ceiling of the sanctum is supported by four pilasters, one at each corner of the sanctum. All these pilasters are similar in design and ornamentation. The base of each of them is carved with half diamond designs. The shaft is plain and is surmounted by a capital of *ghaṭapallava* variety. The capital supports plain brackets with a single volute. Above the brackets rest the plain architrave of the ceiling, the top of which is carved with *gagāarakas*. The ceiling of the sanctum is of *nābhichhanda* variety and consists of five bands of concentric overlapping circles. The top of the ceiling is carved with a full-blown lotus. The *gagāarakas* of the ceiling have been damaged and are mutilated at a number of places. The floor of the sanctum is completely damaged. There is an outlet on the northern wall for *abhisheka* water. As this is a Śiva temple there must have been a *Śivaliṅga* installed on a *yōnipaṭṭa* inside the sanctum, which is now missing. It has been reported that the original *yōnipaṭṭa* of this temple has been removed and installed on a platform at a distance of 100 mt. from the temple.

Sanctum-doorway

The sanctum-doorway consists of five *sākhās* of which the first is carved with a creeper design on which are seen flowers. This creeper is issuing out of a *makara-mukha*. The second *sākhā* is also carved with a creeper issuing out of the mouth of a crocodile. The third *sākhā* is carved with three panels each containing a *mīthuna*. The fourth *sākhā* is a *vyāla sākhā*. The fifth *sākhā* is carved with lotus-petals. The *lalāṭabimba* on the lintel of the sanctum-doorway shows four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* inside a niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a

pl. 18 Śiva temple No. 3, general view from south-east, Barukheda.

makaratorāṇa. Gaṇeśa carries *varadāksha*, *paraśu*, *modaka-pātra* and *kamaṇḍalu* and is seated on a lotus below which is carved a mouse. The niche is flanked on either side by a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga*. On the right end of the lintel of the doorway is carved an image of four-armed Durgā seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying a long *triśūla*, *padma*, chopped off and *kamaṇḍalu*. She wears *jaṭāmukūṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās* and a *sārī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. Below her left folded leg is seen the seated mount lion. Behind the head of Durgā is a circular halo decorated with lotus-petals. On the left end of the lintel of the sanctum doorway is engraved an image of four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *padma*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. Below his left folded leg is carved the seated mount bull. Śiva wears *jaṭāmukūṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *hāra*, a long *mālā*, *keyūras*, *valayas* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. The interspace between the three sculptures of the *lalāṭa* is filled up with eight figures of seated and flying deities. The sculptures show from left to right: (1) A yogī seated in *padmāsana* in *dhyānamudrā*. His head has been chopped off, (2) A flying *gaṇa* in *añjalimudrā*. (3) A flying *gandharva* playing on *viṅā*. (4) A *gaṇa* playing on a *turahi*. (5) & (6) Two yogīs each seated in *padmāsana* in *dhyānamudrā*. (7) A teacher and a disciple seated. The disciple is in *añjalimudrā* and the teacher is holding his right ear by his left hand as to punish him. The right hand of the teacher is placed on his chest.

Each of the *sākhās* of the doorway has been carried over to the lintel. Above the lintel is a projecting *chhādyā* which is decorated on the lower portion with a half-lotus which serves as a canopy above the three main images of the lintel of the doorway. The portion of the wall above the *chhādyā* is plain. On the lower portion of the doorway are carved figure-sculptures. The right flank of the doorway shows a standing figure of the river goddess Gaṅgā in *tribhaṅga*. Both of her hands and legs have been chopped off. Her hair are elaborately and beautifully carved and tied at the back. Her face is deformed and she wears *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *nūpurās* and a *sārī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. On the right of Gaṅgā is a niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a *torāṇa*. Inside the niche is a *Śaiva-dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *mālā*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. He wears *jaṭāmukūṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *hāra*, *yajñōpavīta*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. On the right of the niche is shown a female attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* in *añjalimudrā*.

The left flank of the doorway shows two-armed standing Yamunā wearing *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra* and a *sārī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. Her breasts are very small and not prominent. On the left of Yamunā is a niche containing an image of four-armed *Śaiva-dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *mālā*, *triśūla*, *kapāla* and chopped off. He wears the usual dress and ornaments similar to the *Śaiva-dvārapāla* on the right flank. On the left of the niche is carved a female-attendant standing in *samapāda* in *añjalimudrā*. Her dress and ornaments are similar to those worn by the female attendant on the right flank. The doorsill is carved in the centre with a *mandāraka* decorated with lotus-scrolls and flanked on either side by a *kīrttimukha*. On either side of the *kīrttimukha* is a panel which contains figures of a male

attendant and a seated yogī. In front of the doorway is a *chandraśilā* carved with a *śarīkha* at either end. The doorway measures 1.67 mt. high, 87 cms. wide and 48 cms. deep.

In front of the temple and attached to the *antarāla* was an *ardhamanḍapa* which is now completely missing. The pillars of the *ardhamanḍapa* have been removed and are kept inside the village.

Elevation

The temple stands on a platform measuring 1 mt. high. The *pīṭha* mouldings consists of two plain *bhittas*, one above the other, *jādyakumbha*, *karnikā* and double *kapota*. Above the *pīṭha* mouldings rest the *adhiṣṭhāna* mouldings consisting of a plain *khura*, *ratna-kumbha* carved with half-diamond design and a median band of diamonds and rosettes, *kalaśa*, plain *antarpatra* and double *kapota* decorated with *kuḍūs*. Above this starts the *jañghā* which is decorated with two bands, the lower of which is carved with half-lotus design while the upper is carved with floral design.

Jañghā

The *jañghā* is plain except for a niche on the southern, western and northern *bhadras* containing an image of a seated ascetic of Nātha cult. The niche on the southern *bhadra* shows a Nātha yogī seated in *padmāsana* and holding a *mālā* in his right hand and performing *japa*. His left hand has been chopped off. He wears *jaṭāmukūṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *yajñōpavīta* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. His both hands and the object held by him in his left hand have been chopped off. He is a *kanphaṭā* yogī.

The niche on the western *bhadra* contains an image of a Nātha-yogī seated in *padmāsana* and holding a *Viṅā* by his only surviving right hand. He is in the act of playing of *viṅā*. His nose, mouth, chin and both the hands have been chopped off. He wears *jaṭāmukūṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *yajñōpavīta*, *keyūras*, *valayas* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* carved with flowers. He is a *kanphaṭā* yogī. Each of these niches is composed of two circular pilasters decorated with a vase-and-foliage motif and is surmounted by a *chhādyā*. Above the *chhādyā* are carved two fighting elephants.

Śikhara

Above the *jañghā* rest the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings which consist of double *padma* and *kapota* which support the *kūṭachhādyā*. Above this rests the *pañcharatha śikhara* which is carved on the central projection or *bhadra* with a balcony supported by two brackets. The space between the brackets is decorated with a full-blown lotus. The ceiling of the balcony rests on two pillars decorated with vase-and-foliage motif. The balcony is surmounted by a small pediment above which are carved two *uraha-śrīṅgas*. The *karna śrīṅgas* show two rows on either side of central projection. Each row consists of two miniature *śikharas*. In each of the rows of *karna-śrīṅgas* are seen six miniature *śikharas* above the two larger *śikharas*, each of the four *karnaśrīṅgas* thus consisting of eight miniature *śikharas*. This is one of the characteristics of the *bhūmija* temple. The *āmalaka*, *chandrikā*, *kalaśa* and *bījapūraka* above the *śikhara* are missing.

Sanctum

It measures 1.16 mt. long and 1.88 mt. broad. The northern and southern walls are plain except for a niche in each wall. The niche in the southern wall contains an image of four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying a *paraśu* by his only surviving upper right hand. His head, remaining three hands, right leg and the head of the mount mouse have been chopped off. He wears *hāra*, *yajñōpavīta*, *valayas*, *nūpurās*, and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. A *kamaṇḍalu* is carved in front of his left folded leg. The mount mouse is carved on his right. The niche in the northern wall contains an image of four-armed Bhairava standing in *tribhaṅga* and wearing *jaṭāmukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *muṇḍamālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels and *nūpurās*. It may be noted here that Bhairava has been shown here wearing a *dhotī* and not nude. His head, all hands and both legs have been chopped off. There is the top portion of *triśūla* carved on the left of his head which shows that he held a *triśūla* by one of his left hands. On his right is carved an animal mount and on his left is carved a dog.

Antarāla

The ceiling of the *antarāla* rests on two pilasters each of which has the same design and ornamentation. Each has an octagonal base which supports a shaft which is octagonal in the lower portion, sixteen-sided in the middle portion and circular at the top. The base is decorated with a half-diamond design on each face. The octagonal portion of the shaft is surmounted by a band decorated with foliage i.e., rosettes. The sixteen-sided portion of the shaft is surmounted by a band of lotus-petals. The shaft supports a capital which consists of *karnikā* and *padma*. The capital supports the *bhūta* brackets. Two of the *bhūtas* are shown in *añjalimudrā* and two are shown with *gadā* and shield. While one is shown holding sword and shield, the other is seen holding *gadā* and shield. Above the brackets rest the architrave of the ceiling which is decorated on the lower face with a full-blown double lotus. The architrave supports the flat and plain ceiling of *antarāla*. Each of the niches of the *antarāla* measures 60 cms. high, 43 cms. wide and 10 cms. deep.

Eastern facade

The roof of the *antarāla* is also flat. It supports a balconied window above which are seen two *urahśrīṅgas* on all sides. The *bhadra* on the eastern side is flanked on either side by a vertical row of *karnaśrīṅgas* each row consisting of seven miniature *śikharas*.

There is a *pīpal* tree growing near the northern wall of the temple which should be removed, as it may damage the temple. A number of trees and thorny bushes are growing around the temple which should also be removed. The temple is not at present under the protection of either state or Central Govt. It is a beautiful temple assignable to 13th century A.D. and has good architecture of the Paramaras.

The most distinguishing feature of the temple is that it is made of yellowish sandstone, whereas the other three temples at the site are made of white sandstone. This sandstone has been brought from quarries which are far away. The temple is known as Ratiya Mandir because of its reddish and yellowish sandstone. The platform on which the

temple stands has slightly given way. It is in a ruined condition and requires immediate repairs. It may be noted that it is one of the temples of Natha cult which are so rare in India.

ŚIVA TEMPLE NO. 4

Though originally a Śiva temple, this temple has been converted in recent period into a Viṣṇu temple and is known as temple of Charbhujāji. This temple is still in worship and faces west (pl. 19). It is located on the eastern outskirts of the village. It stands on a platform measuring 78 cms. high and is approached by a flight of five ascending steps. It consists on plan of a *pañcharatha* sanctum, an *antarāla*, a *mahāmaṇḍapa* and an *ardhamāṇḍapa*.

Sanctum

The sanctum measures 1.88 mt. sq. Its walls are plain except for a niche on the northern and southern walls. The niche measures 27 cms. sq. and 23 cms. deep. The ceiling of the sanctum is supported by four pillars, one at each of the four corners. The pilasters are plain and are surmounted by a capital consisting of a *padma* and plain brackets with a single volute. The brackets support the plain architrave of the ceiling which consists of two squares, the smaller one being inside the larger one. The top of the ceiling is carved with a full-blown lotus. The ceiling has become black due to accumulation of smoke. To the western wall of the sanctum is attached a pedestal measuring 83 cms. high, 1.90 mt. long and 57 cms. broad. At present a modern image of four-armed Viṣṇu holding *varada*, *gadā*, *chakra* and *śaṅkha* is installed on this pedestal. It is made of black marble and

pl. 20 Śiva temple No. 4, Surasūṇḍarī
inside a niche on one of the pillars
of mahāmaṇḍapa.

pl. 21 Śiva temple No. 4, A Śaiva deity inside a niche on one of the pillars of mahāmaṇḍapa.

is in worship. The original *śivaliṅga* which was installed in the sanctum on a *yōnipaṭṭa* is now missing. The temple is in worship. The pedestal inside the sanctum consists of plain *khura*, *kumbha*, *kalaśa*, plain *antarpatra* and *kapota*.

Sanctum-doorway

The sanctum-doorway has *pañcha śākhās*, all of which are plain. There are no figure sculptures below the *śākhās*. The lintel of the doorway shows four-armed Gaṇeśa seated on *lalitāsana* and carrying *paraśu*, indistinct, *padma* and *modakapātra*. Above the lintel of the doorway are carved standing *navagrahas*. The heads of Budha, Brihaspati, Śukra and Śani have been chopped off. The doorsill shows a plain *mandāraka* in the centre. The sanctum-doorway measures 1.52 mt. high, 75 cms. wide and 42 cms. deep. The sanctum-doorway has been provided with shutters for the security of the images inside the sanctum. There is a *chandraśilā* in front of the doorway which is decorated with a band of diamonds and rosettes on the borders and two *śaṅkhas*, one on either end.

Antarāla

The northern and southern walls of *antarāla* are plain except for a niche in each wall. Both the niches are lying vacant. Each niche measures 76 cms. high, 29 cms. wide and 21 cms. deep. The ceiling of the *antarāla* is supported by two octagonal pilasters each of which rests on the parapet wall of the *mahāmaṇḍapa*. Each of the pillars has a shaft which is octagonal in the lower portion, sixteen-sided in the middle portion and circular at the top. The shaft is surmounted by a capital consisting of a *padma* and supporting plain brackets with double volute. The brackets support plain architrave of the flat and plain ceiling. The *antarāla* measures 89 mt. long and 1.89 mt. broad.

Mahāmaṇḍapa

The *mahāmaṇḍapa* measures 4.80 mt. long and 4.52 mt. broad. The ceiling of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* is supported by eleven pilasters of which two are in common with the pilasters of *antarāla*, besides four central pillars. The central pillars of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* support the ceiling of the central compartment. These pillars are in two pairs. One of the pillars between the pair has a square base which supports a shaft which is octagonal in the lower portion, sixteen-sided in the middle and circular on the upper portion. The upper portion has an octagonal band in between one pair and two octagonal bands in the other pillars. The shaft supports the capital which consists of a *padma* and supports plain brackets with a single volute. Above the brackets rests the plain architrave of the ceiling.

Each of the pillars of the other pair of pillars consists of an octagonal base decorated with a half-diamond design and a shaft which is square in the lower portion and circular on the upper portion. The lower portion of the shaft shows a niche on each of the four faces. Each niche contains an image of a male-deity standing in *tribhaṅga* (pl. 20). Each of the niches is composed two circular pilasters decorated with a *makara toraṇa*. Most of the deities in the niches belong to Śaiva family as is shown in a Śiva-temple (pl. 21). The upper portion of the shaft is carved with six bands in one pillar while with three bands in the other pillars.

The pillar which shows six bands has the first band decorated with sculptures of seated deities inside the niches. The second band consists of leaves, third consists of dancing males, the fourth band shows dance and music, the fifth band is carved with flying vidyādhara carrying garlands while the sixth is decorated with *kīrttimukhas*. The pillar which has three bands shows the first band carved with diamonds and rosettes and other two bands carved with *kīrttimukhas*. The shaft supports the capital which consists of a *karnīkā* and *padma* and is surmounted by plain brackets.

It is thus evident that both these pillars are different in ornamentation. Above the brackets rests the plain architrave of the ceiling of *mahāmaṇḍapa* which is divided into nine compartments by an arrangement of pillars showing four vertical rows and four horizontal rows of pillars and pilasters. The ceilings of eight compartments are flat while the ceiling of the central compartment is of *nābhichhanda* variety and consists of seven bands of concentric circles and is decorated on the top with a full-blown lotus. It has seven brackets fixed on the lower portion which supported seven figures of deities. However, only one figure of a standing deity holding a *vīṇā* by both the hands has survived. The other figures of deities which decorated the ceiling are missing. There are five holes for holding the figures in position.

The parapet wall of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* measures 82 cms. high. The height of each of the pillars of *mahāmaṇḍapa* measures 2.66 mt., including the bracket. The height of the pilaster over the parapet wall measures 1.83 mt. including the brackets.

The *mahāmaṇḍapa* has a door-way provided with shutters of iron bars, for the safety of the temple. The doorway measures 2.32 mt. high, 1.37 mt. wide and 37 cms. deep.

Elevation

In elevation, the temple shows *adhiṣṭhāna* mouldings which consist of *khura*, *kumbha*, *kalaśa*, plain *antarpatra* and *kapota* decorated with *kuḍūs*. Above the *adhiṣṭhāna* mouldings rests the *jañghā* which is carved on the *bhadra* with a niche which is lying vacant at present.

The *jañghā* is decorated with a plain median band and supports the *varāṇḍikā* mouldings which consist of triple *padmas*. On the topmost *padma* have been provided plain brackets which support the *kūṭachhādyā*.

Above the *kūṭachhādyā* rests the *śikhara* which is decorated with a cluster of *añgaśikharas*. It shows *urahśriṅgas* one above the other on each side. Above the *śikhara* and *āmalaka* occurs *grīvā*.

The mouldings of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* show *vedikā* carved with foliage above which is the plain wall of the temple. Above the *jañghā* are fixed brackets which support the *kūṭa-chhādyā*. The roof of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* is domical on the central compartment and flat on the other compartments.

The temple has been restored heavily and is completely whitewashed with the result that it looks modern. In front of the *mahāmaṇḍapa* was an *ardhamāṇḍapa* only the parapet wall of which has survived. It measures 92 cms. high, 1.04 mt. long and 58 cms. thick. On the upper portion of the parapet wall are sockets. The outer side of the parapet wall of *ardhamāṇḍapa* is decorated with *vedikā* or the railing pillars like the parapet wall of the *mahāmaṇḍapa*. The *ardhamāṇḍapa* measures 1.09 mt. long and 1.06 mt. broad.

In front of the temple is a courtyard which is provided with stone pavement. The temple is in worship and one Shri Bhanwardas Bairagi acts as the priest of the temple. The temple deserves to be protected by the Government.

It is thus evident that the Śiva temples of Barukheda occupy an important place among the Śiva temples built by Paramaras of Malwa during their reign. These temples also bear testimony to the fact that Śiva worship was very popular at Barukheda during the medieval times.¹

Reference

1. Patil, D.R., *A descriptive and classified list of archaeological monuments in Madhya Bharat*, Gwalior, 1952, p. 15.